

Bleaching studies on Al-hole Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) signals in sedimentary quartz

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Abstract

Electron Spin Resonance (ESR) dating of sediments is most commonly used for older sediments (>100ka), since large residual doses render the ESR signal unsuitable for dating young sediments. The multiple-centre approach (utilising both Ti and Al-hole signals) is usually used to test the resetting of the signals used for ESR dating. Here we work towards a better understanding of, and correction for, the residual signal in ESR samples of sedimentary quartz. We undertook multiple-centre ESR measurements using quartz Al-hole and Ti signals on young aeolian samples of different grain sizes which have been independently dated using Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL). Our results demonstrate that Al-hole signals yield residuals indicating equivalent doses of about 500 Gy, substantially older than expected for the known OSL equivalent doses in the range of 8 to 37 Gy. The decay of Al-hole signal as function of bleaching time can be represented by an exponential function with significant residual values. We investigate the dependence of residual magnitude of the Al-hole ESR signal as a function of previous given dose and observe an exponential increase of residual signal with dose. Such observations are consistent with the results of luminescence process

modelling conducted for a model comprising two luminescence centres and several traps one of which being a so-called deep disconnected trap, that cannot be emptied during optical stimulation. As such, we propose that bleaching occurs through an electron-hole recombination process with electrons released from optically sensitive traps. Besides these results that contribute to our understanding of the bleaching mechanisms of the Al-hole ESR signal, we discuss as well the implications of these findings on the procedures used for performing residual dose corrections in ESR dating recommending that when available modern analogues should be used along with laboratory bleached samples for performing residual dose corrections.

Keywords: sedimentary quartz, ESR dating, Al-hole, residual, bleaching, modeling

Highlights

- ESR residuals of Al-hole signals yield hundreds of Gys.
- Residual dose correction mandatory in ESR dating using Al-hole signals.
- Al-hole residuals increase exponentially with preceding given dose.
- Mechanism of Al-hole bleaching by electron-hole recombination is supported.

1. Introduction

The main ESR signals used for dating derive from defects relating to the Al-hole and Ti centres. Two major challenges confront researchers in this field: firstly, the accurate quantification of residual dose contained within the signal is as yet poorly constrained; and secondly, the physical mechanism for Al-hole bleaching, and consequently understanding the nature of the signal which is being used for dating, is inadequately understood, leading to potential flaws in the fundamental assumptions used.

Although sunlight exposure does bleach the ESR intensity of the Al-hole centre, this is not complete

and the signal is reset only to a non-bleachable residual level (Toyoda et al., 2000; Duval et al., 2017). To determine an equivalent dose for sedimentary quartz using the Al-hole centre, it is important that its ESR signal was either zeroed by light at the time of interest, or its initial value can be inferred. Given the often substantial contribution of residual signals to the measured signal of interest in sedimentary quartz, the residual ESR signal needs to be determined, and then subtracted, from the measured ESR intensities prior to equivalent dose determination (Voinchet et al., 2003).

The most widely accepted approach to address this is using a multiple-centre approach (Toyoda et al., 2000); ESR ages are considered accurate only if the equivalent dose (D_e) estimates based on Al-hole and Ti signals agree (Rink et al., 2007). The multiple-centre protocol has since been adopted as standard dating procedure (Duval and Guilarte, 2015 and Duval et al., 2017). Despite this accepted approach, substantial residuals, particularly in the Al-hole signals, are expected when measuring Al-hole signals in ESR measurements, even following prolonged light exposure. As yet, the true magnitude of ESR signal residuals remains poorly quantified. Most authors report residual values as a proportion of natural signal intensity; for example, Walther and Zilles (1994) report a residual level at 44% of the natural, and Voinchet et al. (2003) report a maximum bleached value of 50 % of the natural. Following light exposure for 80 h under a SOL2 solar simulator (equivalent to 53 days of 12 h exposure to sunlight), Rink et al. (2007) observed that the remaining signal was 56% of the natural ESR intensity measured prior to light exposure. Voinchet et al. (2015) examined modern samples from various sedimentary environments (fluvial, marine and aeolian) and reported bleaching rates (% of the total signal that can be bleached) of up to 22%. Tsukamoto et al. (2017), also working with modern aeolian samples, quantified the Al-hole ESR equivalent doses and reported values of >1700, >1200 Gy, 463, 238 and 134 Gy. The first ESR natural dose-response curve for Chinese loess (aeolian sedimentary quartz) was recently derived and indicated an Al-hole intercept at c. 500 Gy (Tsukamoto et al., 2019). This latter approach has yet to be applied systematically and for different types of samples.

Here we aim to investigate possible influences of sedimentary history on the magnitude of residual dose by applying a multiple–aliquot, additive-dose approach to quantify the residual doses of modern and young sedimentary quartz samples of different origins. This investigation has the advantage that the true equivalent dose is known, since all samples have been securely dated using Optically Stimulated Luminescence (OSL).

The second central challenge for ESR dating concerns our modest understanding of the physical bleaching mechanism of Al-hole centres. The uncertainty surrounding this mechanism has broader implications for fundamental assumptions regarding the recombination process and utility of quartz for dating. Al³⁺ is one of the most common substitutional cations replacing Si⁴⁺ within the quartz crystal lattice; charge is compensated by a mono-valent cation (generally Li⁺, Na⁺ or H⁺). It is widely accepted that upon irradiation at room temperature, the defect traps an electronic hole created by ionising irradiation. By this and the diffusion of the cation the Al-hole paramagnetic centre ([AlO₄/h]⁰) is formed. In luminescence dating terminology, this Al-hole defect represents a possible recombination centre. A terminology of deep (unbleachable) aluminium traps and shallow (bleachable) aluminium traps has been used in ESR dating literature to explain the observations on the unbleachable component of the ESR signal (Tissoux et al., 2012, Voinchet et al., 2015). However, density functional theory calculations yield a defect state of 2.2 eV above the valence band edge (Gudmundsdóttir et al., 2015), which is inconsistent with the proposed model. The importance of this Al-hole defect as an electron-hole recombination centre has been previously proposed and widely discussed (Martini et al., 1995; Martini et al., 1999; Itoh et al., 2002; Williams and Spooner 2018). If one considers the bleaching mechanism to be electron-hole recombination, we can expect residuals to be preserved in our signal, for three reasons. Firstly, it is reasonable to assume that this defect is more abundant compared to other impurity-related electron traps since Al is by far the most significant impurity in quartz. In most natural quartz minerals trace element concentration of Al surpasses the concentration of Ti, Ge or other impurity atoms (see Preusser et al., 2009 and

references). This is generally incorporated in luminescence models of quartz (e.g. Bailey, 2001), where the total number of electron traps is assumed to be less than the number of hole traps. Secondly, the bleaching of different thermoluminescence signals in quartz is highly complex (e.g. Chruścińska, and Przegiętka, 2005). Finally, we know that not all electron traps are light sensitive, and have long taken this into account in previous models for optical bleaching of thermoluminescence signals (McKeever, 1994; Chruścińska, 2006).

If the bleaching mechanism of Al-hole signals is electron-hole recombination, then it follows that residual values will likely be dependent on preceding accrued doses. This possibility has rarely been investigated experimentally, even though it poses major problems for dating protocols that apply residual dose corrections. The few investigations which have been undertaken give substantial cause for concern: in one example, samples irradiated with a dose of 6000 Gy on top of the natural and then exposed to the equivalent of 119 days of sunlight yielded signal intensities 12% of the initial value, but still had not reached the same residual level observed in the non-irradiated natural sample (Rink et al., 2007); in another study, dose dependence was observed in quartz from volcanic tephra but not in alluvial quartz (Tissoux et al., 2010). Given the implications for reliable dating of dose-dependent residuals in Al-hole signals, clearly a more systematic study of this phenomenon is required.

In the second part of our study, we investigate the dependence of the Al-hole signal residual doses as a function of given dose for sedimentary quartz samples. We compare our results with the outcomes of computer simulations of the charge carrier transport processes during the irradiation and the optical bleaching.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples

We chose to work with sedimentary quartz samples of different grain sizes from different locations (sand from Australia and loess from Ukraine) that had been previously securely dated by OSL. We selected our samples based on age (since we aimed to investigate modern analogues/young samples); the availability of sufficient material for ESR measurements; and high purity of the quartz extracts. Quartz was extracted according to standard OSL preparation techniques, under subdued red light. More detailed information on sample preparation is provided in the respective OSL dating articles (EVA samples: Fitzsimmons et al., 2014; Rox MIX: Anechitei-Deacu et al., 2018).

Investigations were carried out on different grain-size fractions of coarse ($> 90 \mu\text{m}$) grains. Coarser grains were selected for measurement since we have previously shown that when performing standard measurements of the Al-hole signal, the spectrum is interfered with by a variety of peroxy signals whose intensities are much more significant in smaller grain sizes (Timar-Gabor, 2018), and since it was inferred that this grain size is better bleached and more appropriate for ESR analysis (Voinchet et al., 2015). **Table 1** summarises the relevant sample information. The sample mass was $200 \text{ mg} \pm 5\%$. Mass normalisation was applied for measured signals where relevant.

2.1. Instrumentation and measurement protocols

ESR analyses were carried out using an X band Bruker EMX plus spectrometer equipped with a variable temperature unit. The samples had not been exposed to direct sunlight prior to ESR measurement and their exposure to weak natural light during measurements was restricted to a minimum. Parameters employed for recording Al-hole signals included measurement temperature of 90 K; modulation frequency 100 kHz; modulation amplitude 1 G; 3350 G centerfield; 300 G sweep

width; 120s sweep time; 40 ms conversion time; 40.96 ms time constant; microwave power was 2 mW. A single scan was carried out and the average of two to five measurements was computed.

For titanium centres the measurement temperature was kept at 90 K; modulation frequency 100 kHz; modulation amplitude 1G; 3490 G centerfield with a 220 G sweep width; 22s sweep time; 10s conversion time; 20.48 ms time constant. Microwave power was 10 mW and 20 scans were performed. As in the case of Al-hole signals, the average of two to five measurements was computed. Signals for Al-holes and Ti respectively were quantified using peak to peak height from $g=2.018$ to $g=1.993$ (Toyoda and Falguères, 2003) and $g=1.978$ to $g=1.913$ (Duval and Guilarte, 2015).

Thermoluminescence measurements have been carried out using a Risø TL/OSL DA-20 reader with automated Detection and Stimulation Head (DASH) (Lapp et al., 2015). For these measurements, 9 mm aliquots have been prepared by depositing a monolayer of grains on stainless steel disks.

Irradiation was undertaken at the Centre for Nuclear Technologies, Technical University of Denmark (DTU NUTECH) using a calibrated ^{60}Co -60 gamma cell, with a dose rate of about 2 Gy/s (dose rate to water) at the time of irradiation. Dose rate to quartz was estimated to be $0.941 \pm 2.2\%$ of dose rate to water based on Monte Carlo simulation considering the irradiation geometry used.

Light exposure under controlled laboratory conditions was carried out using an array of TL29D16/09N lamps (spectral characteristics are similar to natural sunlight and can be found in Petrušić et al., 2011), delivering a power of approximately 1000 W/m^2 . We have estimated that one hour of exposure to this lamp corresponds to 1 hour of daylight exposure during summer time.

2.3. Modelling

A kinetic model used in simulations together with the values of kinetic parameters is presented in section 3.3. All calculations have been performed using the differential equation solver – ode15s, which is specially designed in the MATLAB environment for stiff equation sets.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. ESR equivalent doses obtained using modern analogues (young sedimentary samples)

For quantifying the values of the residual dose, we measured young samples that had previously been dated using OSL (equivalent doses of 8, 15 and 37 Gy respectively (Fitzsimmons et al., 2014, Anechitei-Deacu et al., 2018)). Such equivalent doses are effectively negligible for ESR dating given the dose range usually employed in this method. A standard additive dose procedure was applied, the equivalent dose being determined by extrapolation.

The results obtained using both Ti and Al-hole signals for 125-180 μm quartz from Ukrainian loess, and three different grain sizes of quartz (90-125 μm , 125-180 μm and 180-212 μm) from Australian sand, are presented in **Table 1**. The corresponding dose response curves are depicted in **Figure S1** (supplementary material). Despite relative large uncertainties, it is evident that Al signals preserve substantial residual dose values of c. 500 Gy. Quantifying the intensities of the Al-hole ESR signal using peak-to-peak intensities as described by Tsukamoto et al. (2019), resulted in values of the residuals of a similar magnitude.

By comparison, the titanium signals are more easily bleached and yield significantly lower residuals on the order of c. 100Gy, although the large error due to limited number of data points prevents more precise estimation.

Table 1. Summary information on samples investigated. For more information on OSL dating please refer to Fitzsimmons et al., 2014 and Anechitei-Deacu et al., 2018. Dose response curves for both Al-hole and Ti centres from which the equivalent doses were derived are provided in **Figure S1** (supplementary material). The large errors for equivalent dose and residuals for EVA-1002 and EVA1017 are due to the low number of dose points used (natural + 3 doses), since limited material was available for measurement.

Sample (OSL) Code	Grain size (μm)	OSL De (expected ESR De) (Gy)	ESR Al-hole De (Gy)	ESR Ti De (Gy)
EVA 1002: quartz extracted from aeolian sand, Lake Mungo, Australia (Fitzsimmons et al., 2014)	90-125	37	477 \pm 205	115 \pm 49
	125-180		610 \pm 251	98 \pm 11
	180-212		563 \pm 273	169 \pm 94
EVA 1017: quartz extracted from aeolian sand, Lake Mungo, Australia (Fitzsimmons et al., 2014)	90-125	8	701 \pm 386	209 \pm 236
	125-180		658 \pm 323	121 \pm 96
	180-212		647 \pm 366	176 \pm 170
ROX MIX: quartz extracted from Holocene loess soil, Roxolany, Ukraine (Anechitei-Deacu et al., 2019)	125-180	15	508 \pm 65	575 \pm 44

Figure 1 shows that prolonged exposure of samples to light reduces the Ti ESR signal to zero; this is however not the case for Al-hole ESR signal. Even after 1800 h of light exposure, the hyperfine transition of the Al-hole ESR signal (Yokoyama et al., 1985) remains clearly visible (upper panel of **Figure 1**).

Figure 1. Comparison of ESR spectra line shape for Al-hole and Titanium signals from the Rox MIX 125-180 μm quartz sample, prior and subsequent to 1788 hours of light exposure.

3.2. Bleaching kinetics of Al-hole signals and dependence of Al-hole residual dose as function of previous dose

We investigated the effect of bleaching as a function of previous given doses for the Rox MIX sample. Subsamples were given different doses, exposed to light for variable lengths of time (360h, 485h, 585h, 685h, 802h, 1129h, 1629h, and 1788h), with the dose-response curve measured after each exposure. The first exposure (360h) was performed under natural daylight conditions during summertime (equivalent to 30 days of sunlight). All subsequent exposures were carried out under the TL29D16/09N lamps (Section 2.1). The results are shown in **Figure 2**; despite the long exposure times, no signals reach zero.

Figure 2. Magnitude of the Al-hole ESR signals (Rox MIX 125-180 μm quartz) as function of given dose before and after bleaching for different time durations. Black squares correspond to the dose response curve used for equivalent dose estimation (Figure S1). Each data point represents the average of 2 measurements. The lowest dose data point represents the natural. Note the logarithmic scale. For clarity reasons, the dose scale of the natural samples is shifted to 50 Gy.

In order to confirm that these non-zero doses indeed represent residual values for the Al-hole signals following light exposure, we additionally exposed two of the subsamples bleached for 1788h (both aliquots of the natural sample and of material irradiated with c. 10000 Gy) to a high flux of violet photons. After further exposing these subsamples for 10 minutes to the 405 nm (violet) 100 mW power laser in a Risø TL/OSL reader (Jain, 2009), the residual Al-hole signal did not change.

Our experimental results show moreover that larger applied doses result in larger residual values. Prolonged light exposure reduces the natural signal to ~70% of its initial value. In the case of subsamples irradiated with c.1000 Gy in addition to the natural dose, the reduction in natural signal is up to 40%. Furthermore, in the case of an added applied dose of c.40000 Gy, despite the signal being reduced to about 30% of its initial value, the peak-to-peak intensity (expressed as arbitrary units of this residual) is 1.7 times higher than the residual obtained following the bleaching of the natural, and 1.25 times the value of the natural unbleached signal.

For the natural sample as well as for the samples for which laboratory doses were given on top of the natural accrued dose, the magnitude of the remaining Al-hole signal as function of bleaching time can be fitted by a single saturating exponential function of the form:

$$S = A * \exp\left(-\frac{t}{c}\right) + R \quad (1)$$

Where S is the value of the signal measured following an exposure time, A is the amplitude, t is the exposure time, c is a decay constant characteristic of the bleaching process, and R is the residual value.

The results for all investigated doses are presented in **Table S1**. It is important to note that the use of a hyperbolic function (Walther and Zilles, 1994) or a sum of more than one exponential function does not represent the dataset well nor improves the fit.

Figure 3 presents the dependence of the normalized ESR signal as a function of bleaching time recorded for both the natural and 4 irradiated subsamples of sample Rox MIX.

We found that the decay rate did not depend significantly on the preceding dose (column 6 in **Table S1**, supplementary material). This result suggests that the same physical process is taking place irrespective of the magnitude of the given dose, at least in the investigated dose range. However, the value of the residual increases with the previous dose.

Figure 3. Al-hole ESR signals as function of bleaching time for Rox MIX sample. All values are normalised to the value of the unbleached signal. Data are shown for subsamples of the natural and of subsamples receiving four different given doses. Each data point represents the average of 2 to 3 measurements. Dependence was fitted using a single exponential decay function.

The residual values (denoted by R in function (1)) are plotted as a function of previous given dose (**Figure 4**). A single saturating exponential model was observed to represent the trend reasonably well:

$$R = A * \left(1 - \exp\left(-\frac{(D-D_c)}{D_0}\right)\right) \quad (2)$$

Where R is the value of the residual, A is the amplitude, D represents the value of the previous given dose, D_c is the intercept, and D_0 is the dose saturation characteristic.

For the Rox MIX dataset presented in **Figure 4**, values of $A=1.26 \pm 0.64$ a.u., $D_c=16330 \pm 18823$ Gy, and $D_0= 21740 \pm 11947$ Gy were obtained. The large errors are to be expected due to the scatter of the data points, as the residuals were determined by exponential extrapolation of the signal decay with light exposure time. However, it is important to note that the value D_c is consistent to zero within error which means that no residuals are to be expected if the dose is equal to zero. D_0 is a parameter that characterises the onset of saturation of the exponential dependence. For doses larger than $2D_0$ one expects that the residuals do not longer significantly increase with dose.

Figure 4. Values for absolute Al-hole ESR residual signals (a.u.) (sample Rox MIX) represented as a function of previous given dose. The dependence is fitted using a single saturating exponential function. The plotted values of the residuals were obtained based on exponential fitting of signal dependence as a function of bleaching time. Please note the logarithmic scale.

The dependence of the residual with dose, as observed above, can be expected if the Al-hole is acting as a recombination centre, the bleaching mechanism is electron-hole recombination, and electron traps are emptied selectively by exposure to light. Although further work is needed to prove beyond doubt that this mechanism is at play, results of the modelling for simple luminescence models,

presented in the next subsection, show a very similar behaviour of the concentration of holes in recombination centres.

Partial supporting information is obtained by thermoluminescence (TL) measurements. It is still debatable whether one can see the emission of Al-hole defects in TL, however this defect has been proposed as a possible recombination centre. For example, in a recent study Williams and Spooner proposed a model that predicts Al-hole emissions at 380 nm, 394 nm and 408 nm (Williams and Spooner, 2018). We have recorded glow curves for the bleached sample (Rox MIX sample, exposed to lamp for approximately 2000h previously measured by ESR) up to 500 °C reporting emissions in the high temperature (300-500 °C) range under both UV (Hoya U 340; 260-400 nm with maximum transmittance at 340 nm) and blue detection windows (Schott BG-39 and BG-3; 330-480 nm, with maximum transmittance at about 400 nm) (**Figure 5a, b**). The signal detected through the blue filter is significantly more intense than the one detected through the UV window. At this point it remains to be investigated whether these signals represent two separate emissions, or we are partially detecting a strong blue emission through the Hoya filter, especially as the spectral regions of the filters partially overlap.

ESR investigations conducted in our laboratory on heated samples of calibration quartz and other sedimentary quartz samples show that Al-hole signals are fully annealed only at temperatures about 500⁰C (**Figure S2**) as such, Al-hole centres could be a centre involved in the production of these signals. We acknowledge the possibility that other possible recombination centres such as E', peroxy or other non-paramagnetic centres besides Al-hole could also be at play and we are currently investigating this. Nevertheless, the integrals of both these recorded signals are dose dependent, showing a remarkable increase for previous given doses above 10000 Gy (**Figure 5c**), a trend that is very similar to the one observed for the residual Al-hole ESR signal (**Figure 4**).

Figure 5. Average (minimum 5 aliquots per dose) TL glow curves obtained on Rox MIX sample previously irradiated with 2000, 20000 and 40000 Gy, respectively, recorded under Hoya U340 filter (a) and a combination of Schott BG-39 and BG-3 filters (b). The heating rate was 5 °C/s. (c) TL integrals (300-500°C) of the emission presented in (a) and (b) as function of the dose given before the extended bleaching. Please note the log-log scale.

3.3 Simulations of the charge carrier transport during optical bleaching

A series of simulations for a kinetic model including four traps and two recombination centres were carried out in order to determine the concentration of holes in the recombination centres after the

optical bleaching. The model consists of two traps active in OSL process, one shallow trap, one deep trap, which is not thermally or optically emptied in the simulated processes, and two recombination centres. The hole concentration in the recombination centres after the optical bleaching was monitored for various times of irradiation and bleaching.

The following differential equations system have been solved to simulate three successive processes: the trap filling during irradiation, the relaxation after irradiation and the optical stimulation, in the model involving four traps and two recombination centres:

$$\frac{dn_i}{dt} = -s_i \exp(-E_i/kT) - f\sigma_i n_i + A_i(N_i - n_i)n_c; \quad i=1, \dots, 4; \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{dm_j}{dt} = A_{mj}(M_j - m_j)m_v - \beta_j m_j n_c; \quad j=1, 2; \quad (4)$$

$$\frac{dn_c}{dt} = R + \sum_{i=1}^4 [s_i \exp(-E_i/kT) + f\sigma_i n_i - A_i(N_i - n_i)n_c] - \sum_{j=1}^2 \beta_j m_j n_c; \quad (5)$$

$$\frac{dm_v}{dt} = R - \sum_{j=1}^2 A_{mj}(M_j - m_j)m_v; \quad (6)$$

$$\sum_{j=1}^2 m_j + m_v = \sum_{i=1}^4 n_i + n_c; \quad (7)$$

Where N_i (cm^{-3}) and n_i (cm^{-3}), $i=1, \dots, 4$, are the concentrations of trapping states and trapped electrons in the traps, respectively; M_j (cm^{-3}) and m_j (cm^{-3}), $j=1, 2$, are the concentrations of recombination centres and the concentrations of holes trapped in these centres; n_c (cm^{-3}) and m_v (cm^{-3}) are the concentrations of free electrons and holes, respectively; A_i ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), $i=1, \dots, 4$, are the probabilities of electron trapping in the traps, A_{mj} ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$) are the probabilities of hole trapping in the recombination centres, β_j ($\text{cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$), $j=1, 2$, are the probabilities of a free electron recombination with a hole trapped in the recombination centres; R is the intensity of the excitation irradiation producing pairs of free electrons and holes (it is taken as $10^{10} \text{ cm}^{-3} \text{ s}^{-1}$ during the excitation process and 0 for other processes), E_i (eV) and s_i (s^{-1}), $i=1, \dots, 4$, are the depths and the frequency factors of

the traps, respectively; $\sigma_i(\text{cm}^2)$, $i= 1,\dots,4$, are the optical cross-sections of the traps; f – the photon flux density of the light used for the optical stimulation (here $1 \times 10^{15} \text{ cm}^{-2} \text{ s}^{-1}$ during the bleaching, $f = 0$ during the excitation and relaxation).

The values of model parameters that were constant during all simulations are: $A_1 = A_2 = A_3 = A_4 = 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$; $N_1 = N_2 = N_1 = N_2 = 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$; $N_4 = 2 \times 10^{12} \text{ cm}^{-3}$; $\beta_1 = 5 \times 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$; $\beta_2 = 10^{-8} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$; $A_{m1} = A_{m2} = 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^3 \text{ s}^{-1}$; $M_1 = M_2 = 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-3}$; $E_1 = 0.97 \text{ eV}$, $s_1 = 5 \times 10^{12} \text{ s}^{-1}$; $E_2 = 1.6 \text{ eV}$, $s_2 = 5 \times 10^{14} \text{ s}^{-1}$; $E_3 = 2.0 \text{ eV}$, $s_3 = 5 \times 10^{14} \text{ s}^{-1}$; $E_4 = 2.0 \text{ eV}$, $s_4 = 10^{10} \text{ s}^{-1}$; $T = 293 \text{ K}$; $\sigma_1 = 10^{-16} \text{ cm}^2$; $\sigma_2 = 2 \times 10^{-17} \text{ cm}^2$; $\sigma_3 = 5 \times 10^{-18} \text{ cm}^2$.

The simplest possible model was used to approximate the situation present in quartz, meaning the presence of more than one kind of recombination centre as well as more than one kind of trap active in the OSL process, at least one kind of shallow trap and one kind of deep thermally disconnected trap that are also resistant to optical bleaching. However, it should be mentioned that similar effects related to the residual level of hole concentration in recombination centres was also observed for a very simple model including only one recombination centre, one kind of the OSL trap and one kind of deep disconnected trap. The existence of the latter is responsible for the residual level of the hole concentration in recombination centers. Due to charge balance in the crystal, the number of holes in the recombination centers after the optical bleaching is equal to the number of electrons staying in traps. Both depend on the dose applied before optical bleaching.

Figure 6 shows an exemple simulation result for the equal concentrations of the recombination centres and the recombination coefficient of centre 1 assumed to be 5 times higher than of centre 2. The changes of the hole concentrations in the both recombination centres (m_1 and m_2) with the irradiation dose are presented for various times of bleaching. Both recombination centres are populated after bleaching but the residual level of hole concentration after bleaching is significantly lower for the more effective recombination centre. The hole concentration in this centre, for a selected irradiation dose, is also more sensitive to bleaching duration. The inset of figure 6 presents

the outcome of fitting of the residual hole concentration in centre 1 using a single saturating exponential function (as it has been performed for the Al-hole signal residual values in section 3.2).

The quality of fitting is similar to that presented for the experimental data in figure 4.

Figure 6. The dependence of hole concentration in recombination centres on dose for different times of bleaching obtained for a model described in the text. Inset presents an example of fitting the single saturating exponential function of the form $m_1 = A [1 - \exp(-(t - t_c)/ t_D)]$. The parameters obtained

from fitting are $A = 2.39 \pm 0.06 \text{ E11 cm}^{-3}$, $t_c = -2530 \pm 775$, $t_0 = 39050 \pm 4251$)

3.4. Implications for residual dose corrections in ESR dating

Residual dose corrections are trivial if the value of the residual dose is known and does not depend upon previous dose. Such a correction can be performed by subtracting the value of the residual signal (as measured following prolonged exposure to light) from the values of the signals used to construct the dose-response curve. The new, corrected dose-response curve, is then fitted and the corrected equivalent dose obtained by extrapolation (see Tissoux et al., 2012).

However, if residuals are dose-dependent, as implied by our experimental results here, this has significant implications for ESR dating. One cannot know the magnitude of dose accrued in the crystal prior to the bleaching event. As yet there is no entirely satisfactory or universally applicable approach to estimating the value of residual doses preserved within sediment samples. For example, one approach is by using a modern analogue. However, correction by this method is accurate only if an important assumption is fulfilled namely, that the modern analogue sample has the same origin, composition and history as the sample to be dated. Another approach is to conduct laboratory bleaching experiments on the natural sample; however, this leads to an additional residual component derived from the natural irradiation (equivalent dose) on top of the initial, „true” residual. We cannot quantify this value since the natural dose is inherently unknown in our dating procedures. Performing laboratory experiments on additional laboratory irradiated samples leads to even greater uncertainties. These three possibilities are visually represented in **Figure S3**, supplementary material. Fortunately, it is important to note, that at least in the case of the sample investigated here major uncertainties on the obtained residual are introduced only if the dose (i.e. the paleodose) of the natural sample is higher than c. 10000 Gy (note that the values of residuals plotted in **figure 4** do not have a significant variations in the lower dose range). Samples with equivalent doses this high are not routinely dated nor expected to be dated due to saturation concerns on the dose response curve using ESR Al-hole signals.

Here we further test a residual dose correction procedure on sample Rox MIX. For this sample, application of the standard additive dose Al-hole ESR dating procedure without residual correction resulted in an equivalent dose of 508 Gy (**Table 1**). This value substantially overestimates the expected equivalent dose of 15 Gy obtained by OSL dating. **Figure 7** presents the uncorrected and the corrected dose response curves. We performed our correction by subtracting the unbleached component from the natural ESR signal of the Al-hole centre.

We chose to perform dose correction using the residual of the natural bleached sample because this procedure is that most commonly used in dating studies, and is the most reasonable assumption. Choosing a residual value obtained from bleaching experiments of samples irradiated with larger doses would be arbitrary and potentially introduces additional uncertainty. There is furthermore no clear justification for corrections using the residual obtained following bleaching of subsamples irradiated with large doses; for example, the magnitude of the signal attributed to material irradiated with ~40000 Gy is 1.25 times that of the natural unbleached signal (section 3.2).

Figure 7. Dose response of the Al-hole signal of sample Rox MIX, and the corresponding equivalent dose obtained by extrapolation both with and without bleaching correction. The correction was performed by subtracting the value of the residual of the natural signal from the value of each datapoint.

This correction approach substantially improves the accuracy of the equivalent dose obtained for samples of known age, yet the obtained value (195 Gy) is still one order of magnitude higher than the expected equivalent dose (15 Gy). The possibility that other signals are interfering with the Al-hole measurement and are at least partially responsible for this (Timar-Gabor et al., 2018) remains of serious concern and must be addressed in future.

4. Conclusions

In this investigation, we measured equivalent doses of Al-hole centres in young sedimentary quartz samples of known OSL ages, using ESR spectroscopy, and obtained residual values corresponding to doses on the order of c.500 Gy. Such values undermine the accuracy and applicability in using Al-hole signals for dating unless residual dose corrections are performed.

We investigated the dose dependence of residuals in quartz extracted from a Holocene loess soil and observed an exponential increase of residual value with preceding given dose. This result is interpreted in the light of the assumption that the bleaching mechanism of Al-hole signal is electron-hole recombination with electrons released by light from optically sensitive traps. The modelling of such processes using a basic model including four electron traps and two recombination centres was performed and the results allow to draw preliminary conclusions. When the deep traps, which are not emptied during bleaching are present, the residual level of the hole concentration in the recombination centres has a magnitude that depends on the irradiation dose previously delivered and the relation of the efficiency of recombination in the centres participating in the process. Details of the residual level dependency on the mutual relations of the parameters of traps and recombination centres are worth further investigations.

As far as dating applications are concerned, this exponential dependence, if proven to be characteristic to various samples poses significant problems for performing residual dose corrections in ESR dating. We consequently reinforce the application of multiple centres ESR dating and

recommend that: (i) the dose dependence of Al-hole residuals to be tested before applying bleaching corrections, and (ii) modern analogues, when available, may be used in parallel with natural bleached samples for quantifying the values of residuals for Al-hole signals.

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